
THE ROLE OF VITAMINS IN METABOLIC PROCESS

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Annotation.

Vitamins regulate reactions that happen in metabolism, unlike other food components such as macronutrients (eg, fats, carbohydrates, proteins), that they are used in reactions controlled by vitamins. Vitamin deficiency blocks one or more specific metabolic reactions in the cell and, as a consequence, can disturb the metabolic balance in the cell and in the whole organism.

Key words.

Vitamins, macronutrients, fats, carbohydrates, proteins, food, metabolism, cell, organism.

Except from vitamin C (ascorbic acid), all water-soluble vitamins have a catalytic function; that is to say, they act as coenzymes of enzymes that work in energy metabolism or in the metabolism of fats, carbohydrates and proteins. The metabolic importance of water-soluble vitamins is known by their presence in many plant and animal tissues involved in metabolism.

Some of the fat-soluble vitamins form part of the structure of biological membranes or help maintain the integrity (and therefore indirectly the function) of the membranes. Some fat-soluble vitamins may also work at the genetic level by controlling the synthesis of certain enzymes. Unlike water-soluble vitamins, fat-soluble vitamins are necessary for specific functions in highly differentiated and specialized tissues; therefore, their distribution in nature is more selective rather than that of water-soluble vitamins.

Vitamins in all living organisms are not equally separated in nature as they are synthesized in the body or gained from the environment. Some are absent in certain tissues or species; for instance, beta-carotene, which can be turned to vitamin A, is synthesized in plant tissues but not in animal tissues. However, vitamins A and D3 (cholecalciferol) are found only in animal tissues. Both plants and animals are crucial natural sources of vitamins for humans. Since vitamins are not evenly separated in food products, the more limited a person's diet is, the more

likely one or more vitamins are lack of sufficient quantity. Dietary sources of vitamin D are limited, but it can be synthesized in the skin by ultraviolet radiation (from the Sun); therefore, with adequate exposure to sunlight, dietary intake of vitamin D is negligible.

All vitamins can be synthesized or produced commercially from food sources and are available in pharmaceutical preparations for human consumption. Commercial food processing (known as grain milling) often destroys or removes large amounts of vitamins. In most cases, vitamins are replaced by chemicals. Some foods are enriched with vitamins that are not normally found in them (for instance, vitamin D is added to milk). Vitamins can also be lost when food is cooked; for example, heat destroys vitamin A, and water-soluble vitamins can leach from food into water and be disappeared. Some vitamins (e.g. B vitamins, vitamin K) can be synthesized by microorganisms normally found in the intestines of some animals; however, microorganisms usually do not supply the pet with sufficient vitamins.

Requirements for living things to make difference vitamin requirements from species to species, and because of many factors (e.g., genetic variation, relative proportions of other components of food, environmental stressors), it is difficult to determine the amount of vitamin required for a particular organism. Although, there is no universal agreement on human vitamin requirements, the recommended daily vitamin intake is high enough to account for individual variation and normal environmental stressors

There are a number of interactions between vitamins and vitamins and other components of the diet. Interactions can be synergistic (i.e., cooperative) or antagonistic, e.g., metabolic roles (e.g., B vitamins), protective roles (e.g., vitamins A and E), or structural dependence (e.g., cobalt). reflects vitamin B12 molecule).

Inadequate intake of a particular vitamin leads to a characteristic deficiency disease (hypovitaminosis), the severity of which depends on the degree of vitamin deficiency. Symptoms can be specific (eg, functional night blindness of vitamin A deficiency) or non-specific (eg, loss of appetite, failure to grow). Not all symptoms may appear for a particular deficiency disease; furthermore, the nature of the symptoms may vary by species. Some of the effects of vitamin deficiency cannot be reversed by adding the vitamin to the diet, especially if damage to non-regenerative tissues (eg, cornea, nerve tissue, calcified bone) has happened.

Vitamin deficiency can be primary (or dietary), in which case dietary intake is below the normal requirement for the vitamin. Secondary (or conditional) deficiency (even if the food intake is sufficient) can appear if there is a pre-existing disease or stressful situation (for instance, malabsorption of food from the intestine,

chronic alcoholism, repeated pregnancy and lactation). (More information on vitamin deficiencies in humans can be found in Nutritional Diseases.)

Evolution of vitamin depended on the evolution of metabolic processes in primitive life forms required the development of enzyme systems to catalyze the complex sequence of chemical reactions involved in metabolism. Firstly, the environment can supply all the necessary components (including vitamin coenzymes); eventually, these components are synthesized in the body. As higher forms of life involved, the ability to synthesize some of these vitamin coenzymes gradually disappeared.

Since higher plants have no requirements for vitamins or other growth factors, it is assured that they retain the ability to synthesize them. However, amongst insects, niacin, thiamin, riboflavin, vitamin B6, vitamin C, and pantothenic acid are required by several groups. All vertebrates, including humans, require dietary sources of vitamin A, vitamin D, thiamin, riboflavin, vitamin B6, and pantothenic acid; some vertebrates, especially highly developed ones, have additional requirements for other vitamins.

Microbiological analysis is used only for B vitamins. The growth rate of a vitamin-requiring microorganism species is measured in a growth medium containing various identified amounts of food containing an unknown amount of the vitamin. The response to an unknown amount of vitamin (measured as growth rate) is made comparison with that gained from a counted amount of pure vitamin. According to the method of preparation of the food sample, the procedure might indicate the presence of the vitamin in the food sample for the microorganism.

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